

But the breakdown of blast resistance is common in many rice-growing areas, often shortly after the release of culti-

vars with race-specific resistance. We should therefore develop breeding strategies for durable resistance to

reduce the impact of rice blast disease by using the abundant rice genetic resources of Yunnan and Japan. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement — irrigated

Karnataka rice hybrids

R.M. Radhakrishna, B.V. Chandra, S. Lingaraju, and S. Gangadhariah, Regional Research Station, VC Farm, Mandya 571405, Karnataka, India

For more than a decade, farmers in the irrigated area of Karnataka harvested yields of up to 7 t ha⁻¹. No new technologies could help them increase yield further. Therefore, the major objective of the hybrid rice research begun at Mandya was to identify a suitable hybrid that could yield at least 1 t more than the check varieties. This objective was fulfilled by the release in 1994 of Karnataka Rice Hybrid 1 (KRH1) and in 1996 of Karnataka Rice Hybrid 2 (KRH2). The hybrid KRH1 (IR58025A/IR9761-19-1R) has a yield potential of 7.5-8.5 t ha⁻¹ and matures in 125 d. In 150 on-farm irrigated trials conducted in farmers' fields in different districts, KRH1 had a yield advantage of 1.5 t ha⁻¹ over the check varieties. This hybrid possesses field tolerance for major pests and diseases.

Medium-duration hybrid KRH2 (IR58025A and KMR3) matures in 135 d and yields at least 1.0 t ha⁻¹ more than the best check variety, Jaya. In addition, it has a better straw yield and exhibits tolerance for blast. Therefore, farmers are impressed by its performance. This hybrid is semitall with long, slender grains. In 15 other trials conducted at Mandya from 1992 to 1995, KRH2 produced an average of 9.3 t ha⁻¹ with a yield advantage of 1.5 t ha⁻¹ over Jaya. Similarly, multilocation, multiseasonal experiments conducted at different research stations in Karnataka in irrigated areas also confirmed the superiority of KRH2, with at least 1.2 t ha⁻¹ more yield than Jaya. This hybrid was found to be more stable over locations. KRH2 recorded the highest yields in national trials during 1995, with a yield

advantage of more than 0.9 t ha⁻¹ over Jaya.

Agronomic experiments with these hybrids indicated that the recommended dose of 100-50-50 kg NPK ha⁻¹ for semidwarf varieties is also suitable for these hybrids. Planting one seedling hill⁻¹ and 20- × 10-cm spacing are recommended for this hybrid. A seed rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ is sufficient. ■

TNRH16: a salt-tolerant rice hybrid

A.J. Ali, M. Rangaswamy, R. Rajagopalan, S.E.N. Mohamed, and T.S. Manickam, Crop Improvement Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Navalur Kuttappattu, Tiruchirappalli 620009, India

Among abiotic stresses, salinity-alkalinity is the major constraint to yield in rice. Experience in other crops indicates that hybrids perform better than varieties under adverse growing conditions. A study was therefore made to evaluate hybrids involving salt-tolerant parental lines. Ten male sterile lines with their respective B lines and 24 restorer lines were screened under natural salt-stress conditions (pH 9.0

and EC 0.21 dS m⁻¹). Of these, IR62829A, IR66707A, and IR58025A were more tolerant. A similar response was recorded in their respective B lines. Of the 24 restorer lines, only six had good phenotypic acceptability at all stages of growth. Assuming that the additive complementary effect of tolerant A and R lines in the hybrid would enhance the level of salt tolerance, hybrids involving such parental lines were evaluated for salt tolerance. All F₁ hybrids derived using IR62829A and IR58025A as male sterile lines, though poor yielders, proved quite tolerant, with high phenotypic acceptability at all stages of growth from seedling to flowering. A high pollen or spikelet number during the last phase possibly resulted in poor grain yields. TNRH16, derived from moderately salt-tolerant parents (IR58025A/C20R), was the only exception. This hybrid recorded a grain yield of 5,002 kg ha⁻¹, whereas the salt-tolerant check, Co 43, recorded 4,160 kg ha⁻¹. The standard heterosis was 23%. The higher grain yield of TNRH16 may also be attributed to the fact that parental characters for sodicity tolerance get complemented in the F₁ hybrid. ■

Pest resistance — diseases

Differentiation of rice tungro spherical virus variants by RT-PCR and RFLP

M.L.M. Yambao, P.Q. Cabauatan, and O. Azzam, IIRRI

Rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) is one of the two causal agents of rice tungro disease, the most important viral disease of rice in South and Southeast Asia. RTSV assists in the semipersistent transmission of rice

tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV), the other causal agent, which causes the symptoms.

RTSV is a single-stranded RNA virus of 12,180 nucleotides (Hull 1996). Genome organization shows that it encodes a large polyprotein of 393 kDa, which contains the three coat proteins (CP1, CP2, and CP3), motifs for nucleotide triphosphate (NTP) binding domain, protease (PRO), and polymerase (POL). The polyprotein is thought to be cleaved by the virus-